

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Climate drives anuran breeding phenology in a continental perspective as revealed by citizen-collected data

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Supplementary figures

FIGURE S1. Ancestral character reconstructions for phenological patterns of breeding. Reconstructions with the scores of the first (S1; left) and second components (S2; right) of the PCoA obtained from the average of circular phenological data of breeding activity for each species (see main text). The phylogenetic tree follows Jetz and Pyron (2018) keeping 256 terminals (= species).

FIGURE S2. Ancestral character reconstructions for daily patterns of breeding. Reconstructions with the scores of the first (S1; left) and second components (S2; right) of the PCoA obtained from the average of circular phenological data of breeding activity for each species (see text). The phylogenetic tree follows Jetz and Pyron (2018) keeping 256 terminals (= species).

FIGURE S3. Phylogenetic tree used in the ancestral character reconstructions. Here all the 256 terminal names (= species) are shown. Phylogenetic tree follows Jetz and Pyron (2018).

FIGURE S4. General temporal patterns of reproduction in for a) explosive and prolonged breeders and b) species with direct and larval development based on iNaturalist data.

FIGURE S5. Temporal patterns of reproduction in different climate zones for species with a) larval development and b) direct development per climate zone based on iNaturalist data. Climate categories are in shades of blue. Climate abbreviations: Af – Tropical Rainforest, Am – Tropical monsoon, Aw - Tropical savannah, BSh - arid hot steppe, Cfa - temperate hot summer without dry season, Cfb - temperate warm summer

without dry season, Cwa - temperate dry winter hot summer and Cwb - temperate dry winter warm summer.

FIGURE S6. Temporal patterns of reproduction in different climate zones for species with a) prolonged breeding and b) explosive breeding. Climate categories are in shades of blue. Climate abbreviations: Af – Tropical Rainforest, Am – Tropical monsoon, Aw - Tropical savannah, BSh - arid hot steppe, Cfa - temperate hot summer without dry season, Cfb - temperate warm summer without dry season, Cwa - temperate dry winter hot summer and Cwb - temperate dry winter warm summer.

FIGURE S7. Temporal patterns of reproduction in different climate zones for a) Brachycephalidae b) Hyloidea c) Microhylidae d) Odontophrynidae species based on the published literature. Climate categories in shades of blue. Climate abbreviations: Af – Tropical Rainforest, Am – Tropical monsoon, Aw - Tropical savannah, BSh - arid hot steppe, Cfa - temperate hot summer without dry season, Cfb - temperate warm summer without dry season, Cwa - temperate dry winter hot summer and Cwb - temperate dry winter warm summer.

FIGURE S8. Number of breeding observations as a function of non-reproduction observations per months – months are indicated by 1 – January, 2 – February etc.